

TOUGHENING OF POLYLACTIDE/BAMBOO POWDER BIOCOMPOSITE FOR 3D PRINTING

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ABSTRACT

3D printing biocomposite feedstock constituted by bio-based polymers and fillers are increasingly gaining prominence for fused deposition modelling. Along with sustainability also emerges the trade-off of reduced toughness and increased brittleness often causing extrusion melt fracture and ensuing effects thereof. Improving biocomposite toughness through impact modifiers is common, and the present work, we investigate a polylactide/bamboo powder system with two toughening agents: poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) combined with ethylene-co-methyl acrylate glycidyl methacrylate terpolymer as the interfacial compatibiliser, and a commercially-available core/shell impact modifier. We melt compounded polylactide/bamboo powder biocomposites, and extruded as a filament, and utilised a commercially available PLA filament as the baseline. The extruded filament was used to print specimens using fused deposition modelling, and for injection moulding. We analysed the thermo-physical and thermo-mechanical properties of the biocomposite, and assessed the filament quality, surface roughness and processability. The polylactide/bamboo powder (20 phr) biocomposites show higher impact toughness than polylactide feedstock for both 3D printed and IM specimens. The poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)-toughened feedstock exhibits higher impact strength and ductility, filament quality, processability, and lower surface roughness than core/shell-modifier-toughened feedstock.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polylactide (PLA)-based biocomposite feedstock for fused deposition modelling (FDM) has gained increasing attention in recent years because of its renewability and sustainability [1]. However, the addition of biomass materials such as bamboo powder (BP) to PLA causes decreased impact strength [2, 3]. PLA/15 wt.% BP decreased impact strength by approx. 44%, compared with neat PLA [3]. Low-impact-strength biocomposite often breaks during extrusion, and 3D printing. Toughness modification through blending with flexible polymers [4-10], which act as stress concentration sites, is a method to improve their resistance to brittleness, and for producing continuous and constant-diameter filaments.

To that end, an acrylic core-shell impact modifier [4, 5], poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) [7], and ethylene-co-methyl acrylate glycidyl methacrylate (EGMA) terpolymer [8] were investigated as toughening agents for PLA-based biocomposites. The addition of 5 wt.% acrylic core-shell impact modifier led to a five-fold increase in the impact strength of PLA, and further enhanced the impact strength of PLA/wood sawdust biocomposites [4]. The evidence of PBAT impact strength enhancement was also observed in ramie/PLA biocomposite [7]. The combination of EGMA, with functional glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) end groups was effective in improving the interfacial adhesion and impact strength of PLA/PBAT blend [9, 10], PLA/BP biocomposite [11], and PLA/biomass biocomposites [8, 12-14].

In this study, PBAT/EGMA and core-shell acrylic impact modifier (BPM 520) were investigated as toughening agents for PLA/20-phr-BP biocomposites for FDM application. The biocomposite feedstock were prepared by melt extrusion and fabricated to standard specimens by both FDM printing and injection moulding. The toughness properties of biocomposites feedstock were compared with commercial PLA feedstock. The effect of toughness agents on viscoelastic behaviour and processability of biocomposites was evaluated. The filament quality and surface quality of 3D-printed

specimens were also assessed. An optimal toughening agent system for PLA/BP biocomposite was obtained through analysis of mechanical performance. This research provides fundamental data on the effect of toughness modification on the biocomposite feedstock, which facilitates the further application in FDM.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

PLA (4032D) was obtained from NatureWorks, LLC, USA, and PBAT (2003F, melt flow index (MFI): 4.2 g/10 min at 190 °C/2.16 kg) was supplied by Zhejiang Hangzhou Xinfu Pharm Co., Ltd, China. EGMA (Lotader® AX 8900) was purchased from Arkema, Inc., France. BPM 520 was purchased from Dow Chemical Company, USA. BP with a volume-median-diameter (d_{50}) of 75 μm was supplied by Zhejiang Jinque Bamboo Powder Factory, China. A commercial PLA filament (PLA natural) from Shenzhen Esun Industrial Co., Ltd was used as the baseline for comparison.

2.2 Feedstock preparation

The filament feedstock was obtained using a two-stage process. First, the biocomposites pellets were produced by melt-compounding of (a) PLA, (b) toughening agents, and (c) bamboo powder through a parallel twin-screw extruder with a screw diameter of 35 mm and L/D ratio of 44:1. PLA, PBAT, and bamboo powder (BP) was dried to a moisture level below 0.5 wt. % prior to extrusion. The formulations of the samples were 87 phr/13 phr/20 phr/6 phr for PLA/PBAT/BP/EGMA and 100 phr/20 phr/8 phr for PLA/BP/BPM. The combined PLA/PBAT/EGMA system, and PLA/BPM system were considered as a matrix for their corresponding biocomposites. The extrusion temperature was set to 165 °C – 175 °C along the extruder barrel, and the screw rotational speed was set to 146 rpm. Second, the biocomposite pellets were extruded to filament by a single-screw extruder with a screw diameter of 35 mm and L/D ratio of 28:1. The temperatures of the extrusion barrel zones were set to 170 °C, 175 °C, 175 °C, 180 °C and 180 °C, and the screw rotational speed was set to 364 rpm. The filament was drawn along a water bath maintained at 60 °C, at a drawing speed of 345 rpm (linear velocity was around 36.8 m/min), to achieve a filament diameter of 1.75 mm, which is a standard specification for FDM feedstock.

2.3 Specimen preparation

A 3D da Vinci 1.0 Professional printer (XYZ Printing, Inc., Thailand) with a nozzle diameter of 0.40 mm was used for the fabrication of specimens using 3D CAD models of standard tensile (166 mm \times 19 mm \times 3.2 mm, Type I, ASTM D 638) and notched impact (63 mm \times 12.7 mm \times 3.2 mm, ASTM D 256) test specimens. The specimens were printed in a horizontal orientation with the nozzle temperature, heat bed temperature, infill density, layer thickness, and print velocity set at 200 °C, 60 °C, 100 %, 0.15 mm, and 60 mm/s, respectively. IM specimens were prepared using an injection moulding machine (JT-350, Jintong Plastic Machinery Ltd., China) with barrel temperatures set at 165 °C, 175 °C, 175 °C, and 182 °C, and mould temperature set at 45 °C.

2.4 Characterization

Tensile properties of the biocomposites were measured using ASTM D 638 on a CMT 6104 (MTS Systems, China) universal tester at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min under a 10 kN load cell. Notched Izod impact testing was conducted using ASTM D 256 on a XJJU 5.5 J pendulum (Chengde COTs Scientific Instruments Co., Ltd., China) at room temperature. The testing data are based on an average value of at least five tests. The morphologies of cryo-fractured surfaces of IM specimens and impact fracture surfaces of FDM specimens were examined using a JCM6000 scanning electron microscope

(SEM, JEOL, Japan) at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Prior to observation, the fracture surfaces were sputter-coated with a gold layer.

The rheological properties of the biocomposites were investigated using a DHR-2 rheometer (TA Instruments, USA). A parallel plate system with a diameter of 25 mm and a sample gap of 1 mm were used. Tests were conducted in the dynamic frequency sweep mode (0.0628–628 rad/s) with 1% strain, at 190 °C. Melt torque measurements were carried out in an XSS-300 torque rheometer (Shanghai Kechuang Rubber Plastic Mechanical Equipment Co., Ltd., China), the biocomposite pellets were melt extruded through an LSJ 20 plastic extruder with a diameter of 20 mm and L/D of 25:1, the temperatures were set at 150 °C, 170 °C, 175 °C, 175 °C from the feeder to the die, and the extrusion speed was set at 60 rpm.

Filament diameter measurements were performed using a digital Vernier calliper at 3 locations for each position, and the average value was reported. The diameter tolerance was calculated using the difference of the average value and the desired diameter (1.75 mm). Roundness was obtained by subtracting the minimum diameter from the maximum diameter obtained at 3 locations at the same position, based on an industry standard of Shenzhen Esun Industrial Co., Ltd. Stylus method was utilised to determine the surface roughness of the FDM specimens using a MarSurf M 400 unit with a stylus tip diameter of 2 µm, and a tip angle of 90°. The measurements were conducted at a tracing speed of 1.0 mm/s with a trace length of 17.5 mm. Four roughness parameters: arithmetic mean roughness (R_a), root mean square roughness (R_q), mean peak-to-valley height (R_z), and maximum peak-to-valley height (R_{max}), based on ISO 4287 standard.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties are summarised in Figure 1. With the addition of toughening agents and bamboo powder, the tensile strength (Figure 1a) of biocomposites decreased compared to PLA as expected, because of the lower tensile strength of toughening agents and weakening effect of the introduction of BP [3]. PLA/BP/PBAT showed a higher elongation at break (Figure 1c) than PLA for both IM and FDM specimens, demonstrating greater ductility than PLA because of the incorporation of toughening agent with high ductility [15]. On the other side, PLA/BP/BPM exhibited lower elongation at break than PLA for both IM and FDM specimens.

The impact strength is shown in Figure 1d. FDM specimens showed higher impact strength than IM specimens. Toughened biocomposites showed higher impact strength than PLA feedstock for both IM and FDM specimens. PLA/BP/PBAT and PLA/BP/BPM IM specimens showed 47% and 15% greater impact strength, and FDM specimens showed 37% and 7% greater impact strength than corresponding PLA feedstock. PLA/BP/PBAT showed an increase in impact strength compared to PLA/BP/BPM for both IM and FDM specimens, demonstrating the higher toughness of PLA/BP/PBAT, compared with PLA/BP/BPM, attributed to the synergistic effect of both PBAT and reactive EGMA.

Figure 1: Mechanical properties of biocomposites: (a) tensile strength, (b) elongation at break, (c) representative tensile stress-strain curves, and (d) impact strength.

3.2 Fracture morphology

The SEM images for impact fracture surface of FDM specimens and cryo-fractured surfaces of IM specimens are shown in Figure 2. IM specimens showed smoother fracture surfaces than FDM specimen, indicating higher brittleness of IM specimens, compared with FDM sample, which attributed the higher impact strength for FDM specimens against IM specimens. The biocomposites specimens showed ductile deformation as fibrils can be observed on the surfaces, contributing to the higher toughness of biocomposites than PLA. Fibre pull-out and debonding of BP filler from the matrix were observed on the fracture surfaces, indicating the interfacial bonding between bamboo powder and polymer matrix was lower than the internal strength of BP filler, the interfacial bonding was insufficient to provide satisfactory filler-matrix stress transfer [16].

Further BP filler pull-out and debonding from the polymer matrix of PLA/BP/BPM FDM specimen than PLA/BP/PBAT were observed, indicating enhanced interfacial adhesion between BP and PLA/PBAT matrix due to the existence of reactive GMA group, resulting in lower impact strength and elongation at break for PLA/BP/BPM than PLA/BP/PBAT. The PLA/BP/BPM IM specimen showed a lower filler-matrix adhesion because of discernible porosity between bamboo filler and matrix, leading to the lower impact strength than PLA/BP/PBAT [16].

Figure 2: SEM images of impact fracture surfaces of: (a) PLA, (b) PLA/BP/PBAT, and (c) PLA/BP/BPM FDM specimens, and cryo-fractured surfaces of (d) PLA, (e) PLA/BP/PBAT, and (f) PLA/BP/BPM IM specimens.

3.3 Rheological and melt flow behaviour

The rheological properties of biocomposites are shown in Figure 3. The biocomposites showed shear-thinning behaviour (Figure 3b) and lower complex viscosity than PLA at a frequency between 0.4 rad/s and 25 rad/s. The shear-thinning behaviour can be utilized to reduce viscosity and obtain improved melt flow than PLA by adjusting the material throughput and the diameter of 3D printer nozzle [17]. The higher complex viscosity at low frequency are desired for holding the form of filament during extrusion [17]. PLA/BP/PBAT showed increased complex viscosity in the molten state than PLA/BP/BPM, indicating higher melt strength, and steadier extrusion during filament processing, which is advantageous to obtain a filament with consistent diameter and roundness [18]. There was no significant difference in storage (elastic) modulus and loss (viscous) modulus between PLA/BP/PBAT and PLA/BP/BPM, indicating the similar viscoelastic behaviour and mobility of polymer chains in the two biocomposites.

Figure 3: Dynamic frequency sweep plots for biocomposites: (a) storage modulus and loss modulus, (b) complex viscosity as a function of angular frequency at 190 °C.

The melt viscosity for a stabilized morphology were determined by the steady-state melt torque. Figure 4 shows the torque-rheometer plots as a function of time. PLA/BP/PBAT showed a lower melt torque than PLA/BP/BPM, indicating that less energy was required [19] during the process and better processability for PLA/BP/PBAT. The result was in accordance with the MFI (190 °C, 2.16 kg) results of 2.05 g/10 min for PLA/BP/PBAT and 1.55 g/10 min for PLA/BP/BPM.

Figure 4: Melt torque versus time for processing biocomposites.

3.4 3D printing analysis

The filament diameter tolerance and roundness are shown in a box chart, as shown in Figure 5a, b. PLA/BP/PBAT filament exhibited a diameter tolerance and roundness at $-0.05\sim 0.04$ mm and $0\sim 0.02$ mm respectively, demonstrating better quality than corresponding $-0.14\sim 0.13$ mm and $0\sim 0.06$ mm of PLA/BP/BPM filament, because of the relatively higher complex viscosity of PLA/BP/PBAT biocomposite [18]. The surface roughness of FDM-printed specimens was determined and compared in Figure 5d. PLA/BP/BPM parts showed a higher surface roughness with higher value in R_a , R_q , R_z , and R_{max} than PLA/BP/PBAT parts, in agreement with the surface roughness as shown in Figure 5c.

Figure 5: (a) Diameter tolerance, (b) roundness of PLA/BP/PBAT and PLA/BP/BPM filament, (c) 3D printed specimens (1-PLA/BP/PBAT, 2-PLA/BP/BPM), and (d) surface roughness of FDM-printed PLA/BP/PBAT and PLA/BP/BPM specimens.

4. CONCLUSIONS

PBAT/EGMA and BPM520 were used to improve the toughness of PLA/BP biocomposites and investigated the effect on the properties of PLA/BP biocomposites for FDM application. PLA/BP/PBAT and PLA/BP/BPM feedstock was prepared and compared with commercial PLA feedstock. The biocomposites showed higher impact strength than PLA. PLA/BP/PBAT showed highest ductility and impact strength for both IM and FDM products and possessed higher filament quality, smoother surface of FDM-printed parts, and better processability than PLA/BP/BPM. The results showed that PLA/BP/PBAT was a better material for FDM application than PLA/BP/BPM.

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